

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF THE PRESENT STATE OF HEALTH IN UKRAINE

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The article discusses the main mechanisms of management healthcare in Ukraine. Particular attention is paid to the need for changes not only in healthcare management, but also in people's attitudes towards their own health. The main principles of management of medical institutions are analyzed, attention is focused on the introduction of modern management technologies in the optimization of management mechanisms. The basic criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of their application are investigated.

Keywords: healthcare system, management, health, medical institution, mechanisms, efficiency, concept.

The most important task of the modern healthcare system is to create an effective healthcare model. The COVID-19 pandemic, etc., the unstable political situation in the country, and low life expectancy have greatly complicated the situation. It has been proved that the health of the population is one of the priority values of the state policy of any European country. There is no doubt that the current situation requires immediate strategic approaches to health care reform. Healthcare in all countries without exception is one of the priority areas of the social policy of each state and, in many cases, a component of national security [7]. In the institutions of the industry, a transition is needed from predominantly administrative to economic methods of management – personnel management through economic interests, the development of democratic foundations in management, which, in turn, requires changes in planning, financing and stimulating work [5]. Modern political trends in healthcare reform affect all sectors, including the distribution of budgetary resources, the adoption of effective decisions in the field of management. In today's well-known realities, the coordination of the activities of healthcare institutions requires the reformatting of the entire medical industry, in particular, the application of new economic foundations for effective management [2]. The conditions for the functioning of medical institutions need the need to form new effective management systems that are effective for real conditions effective economic mechanisms. The study of the level of effectiveness of the management system is put in the plane of understanding the essence of the concept of "management mechanism" and indicators designed to measure and evaluate the practical effectiveness of the implemented management system: "the effectiveness of the management mechanism is a component of the effectiveness of the organization" [4].

Basic material

Effective healthcare management is impossible without the use of interrelated management decisions, the development of which takes place on multilevel management systems. Current research suggests a set of best practices (best practices) to reinforce the effectiveness of management mechanisms in typical situations to develop a systematic approach to the management of public and private medical institutions

[6]. The main requirements for management systems are formed at the main level of the interstate space; in the future, the norms are transformed under the influence of the socio-economic environment. In the modern realities of economic and social development, health indicators are indicators of the stability of the state.

Purpose: to study and analyze evidence-based and scientific-practical models and principles in the field of healthcare management.

In modern complex management concepts, tools and mechanisms are combinations of methods and management tools that are interconnected by the commonality of one goal. With help formulated mechanisms, the direction and specific parameters of managerial actions are realized.

The problem of developing a systemic mechanism in the healthcare sector is that it is a subject structure consisting of public and private medical institutions in Ukraine [1]. First of all, such changes concern not only commercial structures, but also budgetary institutions, which are gradually turning into communal non-profit enterprises. This raises the need to use innovative mechanisms and means of strategic and financial management (business planning, etc.). The following requirements are imposed on the leader of the new type:

- the ability to use new methods of organization and management, (management of a network of market medical services focused on public health;
- effective management of the quality of medical services provided;
- financial management with a focus on the effectiveness of the organization. Of course, the optimization and structuring of managerial work should be based on innovative approaches to the training of modern managers. An in-depth analysis of this topic shows the practical need for professional training of health managers:

- stimulating the development of motivation for professional training and personal development of health care managers at all levels;

- creation of favorable conditions for obtaining highly professional knowledge and practical skills.

One of the main trends in healthcare management is the creation of a modern system of continuous medical education. The increase in economic,

environmental and social problems in society stimulates the activation of the law and the claim for more active mechanisms for the effective functioning of the entire system of medical education.

Public health has a number of features. The health of the population is one of the most important indicators of the social well-being of society and an indicator of building an effective social states' policies. The level of public health is directly proportional to the investment in this area and the quality of medical services provided, which accordingly leads to a decrease in morbidity and an increase in the duration of the productive period of life. Health reflects a combination of factors: working conditions, the state of the environment, the material and technical base of society, as well as the effectiveness of the functioning of the currently existing healthcare system. In other words, public health is not only an indicator that characterizes the quality of the health of the population, but also a promising indicator of the socio-economic development of society. Low public health indicators, high morbidity affects the quality of human life and leads to economic damage, which is expressed in the following negative trends:

- increase in additional costs for the provision of medical services;
- social payments due to disability;
- decrease in productivity;
- increase in deductions to off-budget trust funds.

A high level of public health is the main component of the state ensuring the quality of life of people, which can only be realized through the creation of an effective system for managing the healthcare system.

The healthcare system as an object of management consists of the following features:

- inclusion in the study big quantity disciplines (medicine, economics, law, psychology, sociology, management, etc.;
 - multifactorial influence of the healthcare system.
- O Ensuring a high level of public health is carried out through the influence of various political aspects.

The training of healthcare management specialists should begin with the creation of healthcare management models, which are based on the fundamental positions and requirements:

- the principle of multi-level influence of managerial actions;
- multidimensionality of the regulatory work of managers;
- non-linearity of modern approaches to the organization of management processes;
- choice alternative options for the development of a controlled system;
- principle identification of a medical organization, taking into account its structure and specifics of activities;
- a set of management models with organizational, information and innovation, technological, economic, components;
- balance of management actions;

- additional regulation of the management system (change in management decisions due to identified deviations in the activities of a medical institution;

- stability of the development of the healthcare system at all levels of its activity.

Be noted that the effectiveness of management models in Ukraine does not achieve the desired result due to financial, organizational, methodological problems, which in turn is reflected in the lack of positive dynamics of the socio-economic development of the state.

An important aspect of the effective functioning of healthcare is the ability to adapt its activities to numerous external and internal factors, which is one of the main indicators in the economic management system. The concept of health management involves a dynamic process of adaptation to constantly changing environmental conditions. This concept should be based on a systematic approach, which forms a set of interrelated elements and processes, and system analysis focuses the management system on obtaining and using resources and the necessary information. The concept of a systemic transformation of the management of the development of Ukrainian medical healthcare institutions should be formed as the construction of an optimal model for significant changes in management. The concept involves a constant spatial analysis of changes in the situation of adaptation of the management system in changing socio-political and economic conditions. The construction of management mechanisms should contain a systematic approach, since it is this approach that forms a set of interrelated elements and focuses the management system on resources and information. This approach makes it possible to introduce into healthcare practice the ability to adapt to political, economic, social changes in connection with the reform

The effectiveness of managerial work directly depends on the quality of training and adequate response of health care leaders to structural changes in the public administration system. Optimum system performance healthcare of Ukraine under the influence of external and internal factors should take into account the development of an appropriate balanced marketing strategy for the management of medical industry, which in the future will create conditions for the formation of demand in the medical services market and the possibility of attracting potential consumers.

Conclusion

For the effective implementation of the health care system in Ukraine, it is necessary to use adequate modern management approaches, high-quality training of leaders of the health care system at all levels, taking into account the application of a systematic approach and analysis of constant risks that may arise in the management process.

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